

Legislative environment, levers and challenges for health data science

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Executive summary

Introduction

The Sudlow Review assessed the health data landscape across the four UK nations, pinpointing areas for enhancement in access processes and governance. The review strongly suggested a unified UK-wide approach to facilitate robust, efficient data sharing aimed at improving health outcomes.

Delay, complexity, uncertainty, inconsistency and duplication in processes related to access to data is often cited as the main hurdle in the use of health data for research and innovation. Detail is important. This paper entitled **Legislative Environment, Levers, and Challenges for Health Data Science** aims to provide detailed information on the legal issues that are relevant to the Sudlow Review's findings, exploring the complex interplay between the common law duty of confidentiality and data protection law as major legal hurdles in health data sharing for research purposes.

This executive summary not only outlines these challenges but also sets out options to improve data access and usage across the UK's health and social care sectors.

Common Law Duty of Confidentiality

Under common law in the UK, patients' health information is deemed confidential when obtained through healthcare interactions. While regulations allow for certain uses of this data, the scope and interpretation vary considerably across England, Wales, Scotland, and Northern Ireland, leading to a fragmented legal landscape. For instance:

- + England & Wales: The law permits data usage with patient consent, or as mandated or permitted by law. Notably, the COPI Regulations under the National Health Service Act 2006 allow for some flexibility in using patient data for non-direct care medical purposes without consent from patients, but these are predominantly for public health purposes, or research approved on a case-by-case basis by the Confidentiality Advisory Group (CAG) of the Health Research Authority (HRA) (although patients can still exercise an opt-out right in respect of this use).
- + Northern Ireland: The local legislation is similar to that of England and Wales but linked regulations, permitting use of information for medical purposes beyond direct care without consent, have not yet been made and so currently patient consent is still required to use confidential patient information for such purposes.
- + Scotland: Caldicott Guardian approval and the Health and Social Care Public Benefit and Privacy Panel (HSC-PBPP) is the pathway for access to NHS confidential patient information for research.

This inconsistency not only complicates compliance for healthcare providers and researchers but also inhibits valuable health research. A broader, more unified, cohesive approach to addressing the common law duty across the UK where patient consent is not feasible would have clear public health benefits.

Data Protection

Data protection in the UK is primarily governed by the UK GDPR and the Data Protection Act 2018, consolidated and amended by the Data (Use & Access) Act 2025 (DUAA). These laws provide robust protection for personal data, especially sensitive health information, which is categorized as special category data. UK data protection law recognises the importance of scientific research, including approved medical research, and facilitates this. Processing for medical purposes, including research, can take place without patient consent so long as appropriate standards are met. However, improvements could be made in respect of:

- + Data Transfers: The stringent rules governing international data transfers pose particular challenges for global collaborative health research efforts.
- + Clear guidance on anonymisation: although recent guidance clarifies certain issues around anonymised datasets, other areas conflict with existing practices of the research community. Guidance specific to the use of de-identified, linked, individual-level data sets in secure data environments (SDEs) would be helpful to resolve this.

These points sound highly technical, but failure to have clear, focused, guidance means that significant time is spent debating legal points that could and should be clarified.

Alignment of governance standards

Even where a path has been identified for compliance with both data protection laws and the common law duty of confidentiality, there remain challenges with access to data for research. Data custodians across the UK have implemented individual processes for assessing and approving data access requests which can be challenging and time-consuming to navigate. This is a particular challenge for researchers seeking to link data from multiple custodians, whereby each data controller often requires the same information in different formats, with multiple review and approval steps. Streamlining and standardising these processes across the many organisations holding health and health- relevant data in the UK would solve many of the current challenges for the research community.

Recommendations

Addressing the common law duty

- + Broader use of the COPI Regulations to permit processing of data relating to “other risks to public health” and wider issuance of COPI notices to address research questions outside of Covid; and
- + Potentially broadening the scope of the Digital Economy Act (DEA) to include health data in the voluntary disclosure provisions, although this risks creating overlap with regime for health data set out in the NHS Act and COPI Regulations and adding complexity and requires careful consideration; and requires careful consideration. The Statistics Board’s accreditation criteria would need to be amended to address health research.

Addressing data protection challenges:

- + Drafting bespoke international data transfer terms for research purposes with accompanying guidance – this could either be done by ICO and/or by the Secretary of State (terms adopted by the Secretary of State could also remove the need for transfer risk assessments).

Addressing lack of clarity around anonymisation of data for research:

- + Additional guidance from the ICO specifically on anonymisation of data accessed for research in SDEs would be helpful.

Addressing divergent governance models:

- + Creating regulator-approved governance models, templates and toolkits which can be used with confidence.

These reforms must be coupled with proactive public engagement efforts to build and maintain trust. Transparency in how data is used, safeguarded, and the benefits derived from research are crucial.

Conclusion

Addressing these layered challenges requires a concerted effort from policymakers, legal experts, healthcare providers, and the research community. The implementation of the recommended changes will facilitate a more integrated, effective approach to health data utilization in the UK, driving forward medical research and innovation while upholding the highest standards of data protection and respect for patient confidentiality. Collaborative, transparent efforts are essential to navigating this complex terrain and achieving a consensus that aligns legal frameworks with the contemporary needs of health science and public welfare.

1 Introduction

- 1.1 The *Sudlow Review*¹ evaluated the current health data landscape across the four nations of the UK. One recommendation made was for the health and social care departments of the four UK nations to set a UK-wide approach for data access processes and proportionate data governance which would include “*Recommending where new or revised legislation will help as well as where clear, consistent interpretation of current legislation and common law requirements would be as effective.*”² To facilitate this, this paper expands on some of the legal issues identified in the report as barriers to data sharing in for health research. These stem from two separate areas of law, but which have overlapping concerns, and which use similar terminology – the **common law duty of confidentiality** and **data protection law**. This paper sets out the barriers encountered under both and proposes options and recommendations for improving data access. Annex 1 contains a summary of the current laws and regulations in table form, to allow comparison.

¹ Available here: <https://zenodo.org/records/13353747>

² Recommendation four on page 163 of the Sudlow Review

2 Common law duty of confidentiality

- 2.1 Patients' health information obtained by health and social care professionals during their care and treatment will normally be confidential under common law. The ability to use confidential patient information for research without consent differs from nation to nation within the UK, so this paper considers each briefly in turn.

England & Wales

- 2.2 As NHS England (NHSE) notes: *“It is generally accepted that information provided by patients or service users to a health or social care service is provided in confidence and must be treated as such so long as it remains capable of identifying the individual it relates to”* and *“The key principle is that information confided should not be used or disclosed further except as originally understood by the confider, or with their subsequent permission.”*³ Unlike UK GDPR, confidentiality survives death. Confidential patient information can be used:

- 2.2.1 With patient consent;
- 2.2.2 Where this is in the public interest;
- 2.2.3 Where the law otherwise requires or permits this.

Patient consent

- 2.3 Confidential patient information can be used and disclosed in line with the patient's consent. It is generally understood that patients give implied consent for use and disclosure of confidential patient information for purposes of direct care, but that consent for wider use or disclosure, including secondary use for research, must be explicit. Again, as explained by NHSE:

“Consent for the necessary sharing of information to support care delivery can be inferred from the fact that an individual agrees to receive that care”.

“Very few individuals ever express concern about information sharing where they see it as necessary to provide their care (for ‘direct care’)”.

“Implied consent is applicable only within the context of direct care of individuals. It refers to instances where the consent of the individual patient can be implied without having to make any positive action, such as giving their verbal agreement for a specific aspect of sharing information to proceed”.

³ See [Section 2: The common law of confidentiality and consent – NHS England Digital](#)

- 2.4 The Health Research Authority (HRA) has produced helpful guidance on seeking consent from research participants⁴.

Public interest

- 2.5 Case law establishes that there can be a defence to an action for breach of confidence where the disclosure was in the public interest. However, the threshold for this is high – for example, the leading case relates to a disclosure of confidential patient information when there was a concern that the patient may pose a risk to the safety of others.⁵ This is a difficult test to satisfy and the circumstances of each individual to whom the information relates need to be considered on a case-by-case basis. This means that the public interest can rarely if ever provide a practicable basis for sharing data for research.

Where the law permits or requires disclosure

- 2.5 The law may either mandate use and/or sharing of confidential patient information or permit this without mandating it. The legislation most relevant here is section 251 of the *National Health Service Act 2006* (“**NHS Act 2006**”) together with the *Health Service (Control of Patient Information) Regulations 2002* (“**COPI Regulations**”), although this is not the only occasion when the law can require confidential patient information to be disclosed – both the courts and other bodies have legal authority to obtain confidential information in support of their duties and functions, e.g. the Care Quality Commission (CQC). However, these other avenues are not suitable for research⁶.
- 2.6 The COPI Regulations address both mandatory sharing of confidential patient data (via Secretary of State directions) and discretionary sharing. Patients have the ability to opt-out of their data being shared for research purposes via the National Data Opt-Out Service.⁷ Regulation 3 of the COPI Regulations is an example of legislation permitting disclosure of confidential patient information, and which can mandate this disclosure where the Secretary of State gives notice under the Regulation. This addresses communicable disease surveillance but can also be used to mandate processing of confidential patient information to diagnose and manage other risks to public health via issuance of “COPI notices”. Regulation 2 (now, in practice, superseded by s.254 Health and Social Care Act) addresses processing of information relating to diagnosis and treatment of neoplasia on a mandatory basis (as well as on a voluntary basis).

⁴ <https://www.hra.nhs.uk/planning-and-improving-research/best-practice/informing-participants-and-seeking-consent/>

⁵ *W v Egdell* [1989] EWCA Civ 13

⁶ The Human Fertilisation & Embryology Authority does have powers to waive confidentiality for purposes of research. This is helpful, but as this paper considers options of use for scientific research more widely we have not addressed it in more detail

⁷ <https://digital.nhs.uk/services/national-data-opt-out>

2.7 Regulations 5 and 6 of the COPI Regulations provide a general framework whereby processing of confidential patient information for medical purposes can be authorised, by the HRA for medical research and by the Secretary of State for other medical purposes, but where the use of information for this purpose is not mandatory. Before the HRA approves processing for purposes of medical research, applicants must seek support from the Confidentiality and Advisory Group (CAG), which advises the HRA on whether the common law duty of confidentiality should be lifted to enable the proposed research to proceed. Research ethics committee approval is a pre-condition for support for the research. Further restrictions and exclusions apply, primarily aligning with data protection requirements. This is the primary method used in England & Wales to lift the common law restriction on processing of confidential patient information for medical research purposes.

Northern Ireland

2.8 The *Health and Social Care (Control of Data Processing) Act (Northern Ireland) 2016* is the legislation in Northern Ireland which provides a similar enabling provision to that in section 251 of the NHS Act.⁸ However, the regulations needed to make this operational have not been promulgated.⁹ Therefore, the only reliable mechanism for use of confidential patient information for research purposes is express consent.

Scotland

2.9 In contrast to the position in England and Wales (and to some extent, Northern Ireland), there is no comparable legal framework in Scotland providing for the lifting of the common law restriction on disclosure of identifiable patient information for secondary use (in the absence of consent).¹⁰ However Caldicott Guardian approval and the Health and Social Care Public Benefit and Privacy Panel (HSC-PBPP) provides a pathway for access to NHS confidential patient information for research.

⁸ See paragraph 20 of [General Medical Council – Confidentiality: Good Practice in Handling Patient Information \(April 2017\)](#)

⁹ See [Revised Code of Practice on Protecting the Confidentiality of Service User Information V2 – April 2019 \(Northern Ireland\)](#)

¹⁰ See paragraph 20 at [General Medical Council – Confidentiality: Good Practice in Handling Patient Information \(April 2017\)](#)
See further [Protecting Patients Confidentiality](#)

Challenges posed by the current situation

- 2.10 First, as highlighted by the summary above, there is currently no effective mechanism that allows access to confidential patient information for medical research purposes, without consent, in Northern Ireland.
- 2.11 In England & Wales, there is a well-established process for this. However, use and disclosure of confidential patient information can only be mandated in the case of: (1) information relating to diagnosis and treatment of neoplasia; or (2) information relating to communicable diseases or other risks to public health. As the *Sudlow Report* makes clear, there is a reluctance amongst many healthcare professionals to share data due to “concerns about the time needed to engage with data sharing and the potential legal liability (for example for inadvertently breaching data protection laws or obligations under the common law duty of confidentiality)”¹¹. While it is crucial to have a process to facilitate those who want to make wider use of confidential patient information for medical research, these constraints mean that there will always be limits to what this permissive (rather than mandatory) structure can achieve.

Options for change

Make more extensive use of section 251 and the COPI Regulations

- 2.12 Regulation 3 of the COPI Regulations addresses processing of confidential patient information for purposes linked to communicable disease surveillance and other risks to public health (i.e. diagnosis, recognising trends, controlling and preventing the spread, and monitoring and managing communicable diseases and public health risks). The Regulation establishes a gateway to processing (including sharing) confidential patient information for these purposes and also allows the Secretary of State to serve notices (“COPI notices”) *requiring* confidential patient information to be processed for this purpose. COPI notices were effectively used to mandate data sharing during the Covid 19 pandemic and could be used more widely to address “other risks to public health” on a mandatory basis.^{12 13}

¹¹ See section 2.3 of the Sudlow Report

¹² There is some doubt whether Regulation 3 of the COPI Regulations could be used in this way. It refers to “recognising trends” which would seem broad enough to cover research. However, other paragraphs in the Regulations explicitly mention research, which may lead to questions as to the legislative intent

¹³ In February 2026, NHS England issued directions mandating collection of data from GPs for research, where participants had given consent (GPES Data for Consented Research Directions 2026 – NHS England Digital). This is not limited to research relating to risks to public health. However, the Directions relate to data where patients have already given consent to use of their data for research; accordingly, the Directions are not being used to lift patient confidentiality

- 2.13 As noted above, this mandated data sharing could only be used for research for one of the purposes identified within Regulation 3 (as described above); other projects (i.e. not for communicable disease surveillance or public health purposes) would still not benefit from extended use of COPI notices and would still need to rely on the process under Regulation 5.
- 2.14 Wider use of the permissive regime for data sharing under Regulation 5 with CAG support and HRA approval could potentially be achieved through the creation of a class-based permission for the use of sufficiently deidentified data for medical research purposes. The standard of deidentification would need to be specified, and individual review maintained for novel or more sensitive research, but once implemented this would enable conforming research projects to avoid the need to go through the CAG/HRA approval process for each individual project, saving time and resources as well as providing greater certainty at an early stage. CAG review provides an important assurance to members of the public, and changes to the existing processes should be considered with the HRA and CAG and with full public transparency and involvement to ensure robust standards for research are maintained.

Amending the Digital Economy Act 2017 (“DEA”)

- 2.15 The *Digital Economy Act 2017* (“**DEA**”) contains provisions which provide a gateway for the *voluntary* disclosure of information held by a public authority to another person for the purposes of accredited ‘research’¹⁴ which is being or will be carried out (section 64(1)). If the information to be shared is personal information, (which is broadly defined in section 64(11) of the DEA as relating to any information that relates to a particular person, but not about the internal administrative arrangements of a public authority) then the DEA prescribes six conditions that must be met for disclosure. These conditions include removal of direct identifiers from the disclosed data and taking reasonable steps to otherwise mitigate identification and a requirement for the research to be accredited by the UK Statistics Authority. One major exception to the voluntary disclosure provisions in section 64 is that it does **not** apply to public authorities with functions relating to the provision of “health services” or adult social care (see section 65(4) of the DEA). The DEA could be amended (with the consent of the Scottish Parliament and Northern Ireland Assembly, so as to facilitate wider sharing in all four nations and given health is a devolved matter) to include health data within its scope¹⁵ by deleting or amending section 65(4) to better facilitate data sharing.

¹⁴ While the term ‘research’ is not defined in the DEA, section 64(8) requires that such research be accredited by the Statistics Board of the UK Statistics Authority under section 71(e), and the Statistics Board must establish and publish conditions to be met by research for accreditation. The latest conditions published by the Statistics Board are here: [Research Code of Practice and Accreditation Criteria – GOV.UK \(www.gov.uk\)](https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/612423/research_code_of_practice_and_accreditation_criteria.pdf)

¹⁵ See Sudlow Review– page 147

- 2.16 The Statistic Board's accreditation criteria do not currently address medical research. The inclusion of medical research would therefore require consequential amendment to the Statistics Board's Research Code of Practice and Accreditation Criteria. In practice, this would also mean that the Statistics Board, and the research advisory panel that advises the national statistician, would need to acquire further expertise in the use of health and social information, likely also involving personnel changes and training to facilitate this. This would be important to maintain public trust. As the *Sudlow Report* identifies this would then create a structure which operates in a similar way to NHS Act 2006 and the COPI Regulations, but with accreditation by the Statistics Board replacing HRA authorisation. The structure would also suffer from the same constraint as HRA authorisations – that it would facilitate sharing by organisations who wish to share data but does not mandate this.
- 2.17 The overlap between the DEA and the NHS Act 2006 / COPI Regulations would need careful consideration to ensure that the relevant remits are clear and facilitate greater, appropriate, data sharing, rather than increasing an already complex and confusing area¹⁶. Amendments to the DEA will need to conform with these provisions to avoid duplication and additional complexity in England and Wales. There are also potential public sensitivities to widening the scope of the DEA to include health data which should be carefully considered in consultation with public and patients as well as the National Data Guardian. There is a lack of consensus amongst the research community as to whether amendment to the DEA to bring health data into scope would enable research or create overlap and further confusion.

¹⁶ There are current proposals to amend the DEA, contained in the English Devolution Whitepaper, published on 16th December 2024. These do not address the suggestion outlined above and in the Sudlow Report

Make more extensive use of the Statistics and Registration Service Act 2007

2.18 It is also helpful to note the opportunity to access health data presented by the UK Statistics Authority (and the Office for National Statistics (“**ONS**”) as its executive office). Under section 45C of the *Statistics and Registration Service Act 2007* (“**SRSA**”), the ONS can require certain public authorities (such as NHS England) to provide information that the public authority holds in relation to its functions which the ONS needs to be able to exercise one or more of its own functions (i.e. preparation of certain statistics). This is quite straightforward for public authorities in England but less so for those in Wales and Scotland which require permission from ministers for the ONS to exercise this power. The ONS is permitted to disclose “personal information” which it holds to “approved researchers” (section 39(4) SRSA) provided the person who disclosed the information to the ONS consents to this further disclosure (section 45E(3) SRSA). The term approved researcher is broadly defined and means “*an individual to whom the Board [the ONS] has granted access, for the purposes of statistical research, to personal information held by it*”. This definition is expanded upon by the ONS in its guidance on accessing data held by the ONS¹⁷ which provides that the “*prerequisites and process for becoming an approved researcher are the same as those for accredited researchers under the Digital Economy Act 2017*” and links to Part 2 of the Research Code of Practice and Accreditation Criteria.¹⁸ This includes more detailed requirements (e.g. need for an undergraduate degree or higher including a “significant” proportion of mathematics or statistics). The code also requires research projects to be accredited if making use of the data provided under the SRSA or DEA. Put together, this would enable the ONS to obtain NHS data and share this with non-governmental researchers provided they satisfy its requirements for access and the NHS body providing the data consents to this further disclosure. This capability can streamline access to crucial data while ensuring ongoing protection of patient confidentiality and adherence to stringent data protection policies. As the consent of health and social care providers would be needed, there may still be institutional reluctance to give this consent. This could be addressed through further guidance on when it would be suitable to grant this consent without the disclosing body being in breach of confidentiality or data protection rules.

¹⁷ See <https://www.ons.gov.uk/aboutus/whatwedo/statistics/requestingstatistics/secureresearchservice/becomeanaccreditedresearcher#access-using-the-srsa-approved-researcher-legal-gateway>

¹⁸ <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/digital-economy-act-2017-part-5-codes-of-practice/research-code-of-practice-and-accreditation-criteria#section-b-accreditation-of-researchers-and-peer-reviewers>

Amendments instead of a new regime

- 2.19 This paper proposes amendments and extensions to the current laws rather than creation of something entirely new. Currently, for research making use of section 251, few participants raise objections, nor do many exercise their data subject rights in relation to research projects. We suggest that it would make more sense to expand these frameworks rather than introduce something entirely new which may be off putting to the general public.
- 2.20 However, as shown by the public reaction to the “NHS Data Grab”¹⁹, in some cases the public is not comfortable with the government controlling/possessing their health data with some preferring an approach where health data and non-health data are governed by different regulations. Although expanding the DEA may assist with data sharing it will be important to consider public perception and so transparency and awareness will be vital to avoid inadvertently driving opt outs.
- 2.21 Feedback from some in the research community is that concerns over the difficulties in navigating patient confidentiality at some organisations have led them to become risk-averse and to steer away from data sharing (with both the ICO and the NDG producing guidance reminding that data sharing is permitted and indeed encouraged in certain circumstances). Charities and smaller research organisations may not have the financial resources for expert legal advice. These considerations suggest that any changes or new frameworks will need to be accompanied by very clear guidance for the research community.

¹⁹ See for example this news article: <https://www.theguardian.com/society/2021/aug/22/nhs-data-grab-on-hold-as-millions-opt-out>

3 Data protection

- 3.1 Data protection in the UK is currently governed by the *UK GDPR* and *Data Protection Act 2018* (“**DPA 2018**”), as recently consolidated and amended by the *Data (Use and Access) Act 2025* (altogether “**data protection legislation**”). Data protection legislation applies to **personal data**. This is a broad concept and defined in UK GDPR as “*any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person*” (Art. 4(1)). This includes direct identifiers (such as names and identification numbers) but also less “obvious” data such as IP addresses. The legislation also states that a person can be identified or identifiable by reference to factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic and mental identity of a natural person. Data protection legislation protects all personal data. However, certain “special categories” of personal data are given additional protection; this includes genetic data and data concerning health.
- 3.2 The rules governing the processing of personal data do not apply to the personal data of deceased individuals (Recital 27 UK GDPR), unlike the common law duty of confidentiality, which continues to apply even after the death of the person to whom the confidential information relates. Furthermore, data is only personal data to the extent it is **identifiable**, so anonymised data is not subject to the same restrictions under UK GDPR or the DPA 2018.²⁰
- 3.3 The obligations under UK data protection legislation differ between parties depending on their role as controller or processor for the research. In this section we have summarised the obligations applicable to controllers as these are the more extensive. Processors are only subject to a subset of these obligations.
- 3.4 This paper summarises provisions in data protection legislation which address similar areas to those relevant to the law of confidence – i.e. when patient information can be used / disclosed without consent for medical purposes. These are set out in:
 - 3.4.1 The requirement for a lawful basis for processing and the prohibition on processing special categories of data (Arts. 6 & 9 UK GDPR); and
 - 3.4.2 The purpose limitation principle (Art.5(1)b), Art.8A, and Art.84B UK GDPR).

²⁰ This question of anonymisation is also important under the common law duty of confidentiality as if information is anonymised it cannot be confidential patient information and so the rules of confidentiality will not apply. This is discussed further below

3.5 In addition, we have also summarised two provisions which have no equivalent in the law of confidence but which can impact medical research:

3.5.1 Transparency (Arts. 13 & 14); and

3.5.2 Restrictions on data transfers (Arts. 44A – 49A)²¹.

Lawful basis

3.6 Art.6 UK GDPR provides that it is only lawful to process personal data if the processing meets one of the lawful bases set out in Article 6. The lawful bases most relevant for research purposes are:

3.6.1 6(1)(a) consent

3.6.2 6(1)(e) processing is necessary for the performance of a task in the public interest

3.6.3 6(1)(f) processing is necessary for legitimate interests of the controller, or another party, except where those interests are overridden by the data subjects' interests (this condition is not available for processing which is carried out by a public body fulfilling its functions).

3.7 Similarly, Art.9 prohibits processing of special category data, which includes data concerning health, unless one of a number of conditions set out in Article 9 or Schedule 1 to the DPA 2018 is met. Articles 6 and 9 are cumulative. Relevant conditions here are:

3.7.1 9(2)(a) Consent (this time explicit)

3.7.2 9(2)(j) and Sch. 1, para 4 – processing is necessary for (ia) scientific research purposes and is in the public interest.

3.7.3 Articles 84B and 84C set out additional safeguards, including that if the processing is for the purposes of taking measures or decisions with respect to a particular individual, that the research must be approved medical research. In addition, Art.84C UK GDPR provides that the safeguards must include technical and organisational measures to ensure personal data collection is minimised, for example through pseudonymisation.

²¹ Data protection legislation also contains provisions relating to data quality; data retention; security; individual's rights; relationships with processors and joint controllers; and accountability obligations, including record-keeping obligations and obligations to appoint a data protection officer. However, these do not generally pose inappropriate challenges for processing for medical purposes

- 3.8 Consent has a specific meaning under data protection law. It must be “freely given”, which recital 42 notes will not be the case if “*the data subject ... is unable to refuse or withdraw consent without detriment*”. An individual who withdraws consent to treatment may well suffer detriment as a result, but this would not invalidate consent to treatment or to participate in a clinical trial.²² Further, if a controller’s sole lawful basis for processing is consent and an individual withdraws consent to processing of their data, then the controller must stop processing and should delete the data. Data processed based on consent for research purposes would therefore have to be deleted.²³ Unlike consent under the law of confidence, consent for data protection purposes, therefore, is not merely concerned with respecting the integrity and choice of the data subject: it is only suitable as a lawful basis for processing which is entirely at the discretion of the data subject.
- 3.9 For this reason, although consent is theoretically a lawful basis for processing personal data, organisations processing personal data for medical purposes are unlikely to rely on this basis. However, this is not problematic in practice; other lawful bases are readily available with guidance from the HRA and ICO²⁴ noting that organisations should rely on Art. 6(1)(e) or (f) as the lawful basis and Art. 9(2)(j) as the condition for processing for medical research purposes.
- 3.10 Recent changes in the DUAA clarify the definition of consent in the context of scientific research. Recital 33 already made clear that researchers can seek consent for the processing of personal data in broad areas of scientific research, even if it is not possible to fully specify all research purposes at the time consent is collected. This must be consistent with generally recognised ethical standards relevant to the area of research, and data subjects must be given the opportunity (where possible) to consent only to part of the research, rather than being forced to consent to all uses. The DUAA amends Article 4 of the UK GDPR to put this principle into the main text, as opposed to the recitals.

²² The EDPB’s Opinion 3/2019 concerning the Questions and Answers on the interplay between the Clinical Trials Regulation (CTR) and the General Data Protection regulation (GDPR) (art. 70.1.b)) (paras 15 to 21) suggests that the fact that an individual is not in good health, or belongs to a socially or economically dependent group would, of itself, mean that consent is not freely given

²³ EDPB Opinion 3/2019 paras 23 & 24

²⁴ HRA guidance – <https://www.hra.nhs.uk/planning-and-improving-research/policies-standards-legislation/data-protection-and-information-governance/gdpr-guidance/>
ICO guidance – <https://ico.org.uk/media2/migrated/4019614/research-provisions-draft-consultation-202202.pdf>

Purpose limitation

- 3.11 Art.5(1)(b) UK GDPR provides that personal data shall be “*collected (whether from the data subject or otherwise) for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes and not further processed by or on behalf of a controller in a manner that is incompatible with the purposes for which the controller collected the data*”. However, Art. 8A provides that “*processing for a new purpose is to be treated as processing in a manner compatible with the original purpose where... for the purpose of scientific .. research*” (so long as it follows the requirements of Article 84B). Provisions previously in the recitals to UK GDPR, which make clear that ‘scientific research’ includes any research that can reasonably be described as scientific, regardless of whether it’s publicly or privately funded, or commercial or non-commercial have been moved from the recitals to the main text of the legislation.
- 3.12 As with the conditions relating to scientific research mentioned above, Art.84C UK GDPR is relevant, which provides that the research must be carried out with appropriate safeguards.
- 3.13 It follows that the provisions of data protection legislation are considerably more flexible than the law of confidence and processing of personal data for purposes of scientific research is given a privileged status.²⁵

Transparency

- 3.14 UK GDPR requires that personal data must be processed in a transparent manner and that specified information must be provided to individuals (for example via a privacy notice). These requirements can be problematic for secondary uses of personal data for research purposes.

²⁵ The Data Use & Access Act contains amendments to the provisions on purpose limitation. Although the provisions are phrased and set out differently, they largely restate the existing law. For processing where the lawful basis for processing is consent, the provisions of the Act are more restrictive as they provide that the data subject must give consent to any secondary use of the data for research purposes

- 3.15 UK GDPR requires the controller to provide detailed information (such as the purposes of the processing, the categories of data to be processed and details of recipients or categories of recipients of the data) to the data subject. If these details change, then the controller must provide updated information to data subjects. UK GDPR contains two similar sets of obligations: Art.13 applies when the controller collects personal data directly from data subjects; Art. 14 applies where data has not been obtained directly from the data subject (for example, when it is obtained from another organisation). Where data has been collected indirectly there is an exemption to providing this information where it is impossible or would involve a disproportionate effort to do so or where doing so “*is likely to render impossible or seriously impair the achievement of the objectives of that processing*”. This exemption applies “*in particular for processing for scientific ... research purposes...*”. However, there is currently no such exemption for directly collected data, meaning that where a controller now wishes to make further use itself, or to share, personal data that it collected directly, it must inform individuals of this new processing. This can be problematic as the controller may no longer possess contact details for the data subject to notify them of the processing and it is often prohibitively expensive to do so due to the number of individuals contained in a dataset and the need to possibly access archived data.
- 3.16 This issue has been resolved through the DUAA. The DUAA gives controllers who have collected data directly from data subjects, and who now wish to make further use of the data for purposes of scientific research, a similar exemption to that which is available for data controllers who have collected personal data indirectly. The DUAA inserts such an exemption at Art.13(5) UK GDPR where the further processing is for the purposes of scientific research (amongst other things).

Data transfers

- 3.17 UK GDPR provides that data is “transferred” where the data is processed by a person in another country, even if the data does not physically move e.g. because it is in a secure data environment (SDE).
- 3.18 UK GDPR prohibits transfers of personal data to another country or to an international organisation unless the recipient has been recognised as providing an adequate level of protection for data subjects, or appropriate safeguards have been put in place (Art. 46(1A) UK GDPR)²⁶. As very few countries²⁷ and, (so far) no international organisations have been recognised as providing an adequate level of protection this means that appropriate safeguards must be put in place. The available safeguards are prescribed by UK GDPR. While this restriction is burdensome for all organisations, it can be prohibitive for organisations who wish to transfer personal data outside the UK for research purposes – especially where the recipient research institution is a public authority or a US federally funded body.

²⁶ There are exceptions to this provision. However, they are interpreted narrowly and while they can sometimes assist in one-off transfers they are not suitable for data transfers which are more than occasional and non-repetitive

²⁷ <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/uk-gdpr-guidance-and-resources/international-transfers/international-transfers-a-guide/#Q1>

- 3.19 The current main safeguards are the UK Bridge to the Data Privacy Framework (transfers to the US only), standard data protection clauses adopted by the ICO, Binding Corporate Rules approved by the ICO, and finally administrative arrangements between public institutions which include enforceable and effective data subject rights.²⁸ Working through each safeguard in turn:
- 3.19.1 UK Bridge to the Data Privacy Framework – this only applies to transfers to the US. Further recipients must be regulated by either the Federal Trade Commission (FTC) or Department of Transportation (DoT) in the US, which rules out many types of organisations involved in research – for example not-for-profits.
 - 3.19.2 Standard contractual clauses adopted by ICO – this is the most widely used safeguard for data transfers. However, these clauses require that the recipient agree to the governing law and jurisdiction being that of a UK nation. On policy grounds, most public bodies outside the UK are not permitted to agree to such provisions. They are also not suitable for federally funded US research institutions, which are also subject to a policy prohibition on agreeing to this.²⁹
 - 3.19.3 Binding Corporate Rules – these can only be used for transfers or personal data within a group of undertakings or enterprises (for example, a corporate group). They cannot be used for transfers between arms-length organisations. Additionally, they are costly and time consuming to obtain which makes them a poor choice in research.
 - 3.19.4 Administrative arrangements between public bodies and other relevant person(s) – these require case by case approval from the ICO. The uncertainty and time involved would be off-putting for most research projects.

The Secretary of State has the power to recognise new transfer mechanisms for allowing international personal data transfers, although this power has not been used to date.

²⁸ Under UK GDPR approved codes of conduct and certification mechanisms can be relied on but currently there are none approved in the UK for this purpose

²⁹ See this article for further detail on the issues posed by international transfers – https://www.ga4gh.org/news_item/ga4gh-gdpr-brief-navigating-international-data-transfers-under-gdpr-impediments-facing-us-federal-science-agencies-and-research-universities/

- 3.20 In addition, UK GDPR also allows transfers to take place on the basis of a legally binding and enforceable agreement between public bodies and other relevant persons. These do not need to be authorised by ICO. This is rarely relied on because a) there is no certainty as to what must be included in such agreements (there is some guidance on equivalent EU provisions, but no UK guidance); and until recently the mechanism was only available between public bodies so was not available if one party was a private sector organisation.
- 3.21 Further helpful changes could be made and should be readily achievable. In particular, the ICO could work with research organisations to adopt standard contractual clauses which could be used by research organisations, but which do not require a UK national governing law and jurisdiction clause. Alternatively, ICO could work with research organisations to issue guidance on acceptable forms of legally binding and enforceable instruments, ideally including template drafting. New guidance should accompany these terms to explain when they should be used and also to make clear that the ICO considers such transfers as low risk where the data remains in an SDE and does not physically move. This will reduce the need for risk assessments and improve confidence across the sector as many organisations currently hesitate to transfer data internationally due to the perceived level of risk).
- 3.22 As well as being required to implement an appropriate safeguard, organisations must also complete a transfer risk assessment which considers the measures put in place for that particular transfer/recipient and the laws and practices in the country or international organisation. Such risk assessments further complicate transfers. The DUAA allows this process to be lighter touch for low-risk transfers. In addition, the DUAA allows the Secretary of State to specify standard data protection clauses where transfer risk assessments are automatically deemed to be met. The issuance of such clauses for use in connection with SDEs, where risks to individuals are appropriately mitigated, would remove this impediment to transfers.

Other provisions relating to scientific research

There are specific provisions within UK GDPR and the DPA 2018 to facilitate the use of personal data for scientific research purposes with such use not generally being problematic (although in practice this is not always the case as noted below). Article 84B UK GDPR provides that, so long as appropriate safeguards to protect to the rights and freedoms of the data subject are implemented, then where processing is for the purpose of scientific research certain obligations such as requirements relating to notice, further processing of data, retention and individual rights are somewhat relaxed – for example erasure requests do not need to be fulfilled where erasure would render “*impossible or seriously impair*” the objectives of the research, Art.17(3)(d) UK GDPR. Sch.2, para 27 DPA 2018 provides further exemptions where processing is for the purpose of scientific research which further simplifies the compliance requirements.

Other obligations

- 3.23 As detailed above there are several issues faced by researchers when trying to access personal data in the UK and enable international research collaborations. The fact there are multiple issues is in itself problematic as each problem takes time and resources to resolve in addition to making organisations nervous about data sharing.³⁰ To resolve these issues advantage should be taken of synergies between the various pieces of legislation that apply so that organisations do not have to jump between different laws to be able to share data for research purposes.

³⁰ See for example the experiences of the authors of this paper when trying to obtain data for a study and how multiple problems compounded the time taken for access to data. <https://bmjopen.bmj.com/content/11/8/e047575>

4 Data that does not identify individuals

- 4.1 As noted above, and as stated in recital 26 of UK GDPR, data protection legislation “*does not.. concern the processing of.. anonymous information, including for statistical or research purposes*”. Similarly, and as also noted above, obligations of confidentiality are stated to apply only when patients are identifiable. This raises the obvious question as to whether it is possible to carry out health research using data which is not identifiable (i.e. anonymous data), so that the law would recognise that there is no need to for data protection or the law of confidence to restrict that research.

Position under data protection legislation and ICO guidance on the topic

- 4.2 As mentioned above, per Art.4(1) UK GDPR, “personal data” means “*any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person*”, who may be identified “*directly or indirectly*”. The ICO issued new guidance on anonymisation in March 2025 which explains the terms anonymisation and pseudonymisation and provides practical advice on ways to anonymise personal data while complying with data protection law. Although the guidance is not specific to scientific research and SDEs, it clarifies some relevant issues³¹.
- 4.3 In assessing whether an individual may be identifiable, ICO suggests looking at two factors: whether the individual can be singled out, and whether information about the individual can be linked together to identify them. The ICO also suggests looking at whether information revealing the individual’s identity can be inferred from the information.
- 4.4 Recital 26 UK GDPR states that one must look at “*all means reasonably likely to be used by the controller or by another person*”, taking account of “*all objective factors, such as the costs of and the amount of time required for identification, taking into consideration the available technology at the time of the processing and technological developments*”. The ICO’s guidance expands on this, explaining that “*the key is what is ‘reasonably likely’ relative to the circumstances, not what may be independently ‘conceivably likely’*.”

³¹ See “What are the key indicators of identifiability?” in the ICO’s guidance on anonymisation available at <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/uk-gdpr-guidance-and-resources/data-sharing/anonymisation/how-do-we-ensure-anonymisation-is-effective/#keyindicatorsofidentifiability>

- 4.5 The ICO provides that data extracted from a source dataset can still be considered anonymous if the source dataset still exists somewhere; it depends on who has access to that dataset. The ICO calls this the ‘whose hands’ question, where the status of the information should be considered in the different ‘hands’ of those who process it. The status of the data in the hands of the recipient rather than the disclosing party is what matters. If the likelihood of identifying an individual is “sufficiently remote” in their hands, then the data is “effectively anonymised.” The guidance also suggests employing the “motivated intruder” test to test the likelihood of somebody successfully attempting to identify individuals from the data³². Recent EU case law confirms that if pseudonymous data is disclosed by one party to another, the information may be anonymous in the hands of the recipient where it is not reasonably likely that the recipient can identify individuals³³. This is similar to the ICO position. EU data protection authorities have committed to publish further guidance on this, but this has not yet happened.
- 4.6 Helpfully, the ICO guidance also clarifies that if one record in a dataset can be isolated, this does not automatically mean the person it relates to is identifiable. One would also need to consider whether additional data sources could narrow down the pool of possible individuals or enable actions targeting a specific person (even if their ‘real-world’ identity remains unknown).
- 4.7 The ICO’s guidance also provides advice on practical implementation relevant to scientific research. It recommends adopting generalisation (which reduces specificity of the data by changing information such that it relates to multiple people e.g. using age bands instead of exact age) and randomisation (reducing certainty of a record relating to a particular person e.g. small increases or decreases to the height of participants without changing the mean of the distribution) approaches to anonymisation techniques.
- 4.8 One measure commonly used to protect patients’ identity in research is key-coding, where an identifier (such as name or NHS number) is replaced with an alternate code and where the access to the look-up table needed to re-identify the patient is restricted. This would fall within UK GDPR’s definition of “pseudonymisation” – namely, “*processing of personal data in such a manner that the personal data can no longer be attributed to a specific data subject without the use of additional information, provide that such additional information is kept separately and is subject to technical and organisational measures to ensure that the personal data are not attributed to an identified or identifiable person*” (art.4(5)). Recital 26 makes clear that “*personal data which have undergone pseudonymisation ... should be considered to be information on an identifiable person*” – in other words, this still counts as personal data.

³² The “motivated intruder test” assesses the likelihood of success of a (i) reasonably competent individual; (ii) accessing appropriate resources; and (iii) using investigative techniques to identify someone from anonymous information

³³ EDPS v SRB, 2025 ([The Court of Justice clarifies the scope of the concept of personal data in the context of a transfer of pseudonymised data to third parties](#))

- 4.9 Another commonly used measure to protect privacy is encryption. Here, guidance from ICO is that this is a security measure; it does not make data anonymous as whoever has the key can remove the encryption to access the full data. It *is* possible to anonymise patient data. However, as these examples illustrate, methods that are commonly used to protect privacy are often not sufficient.
- 4.10 As explained above, pseudonymised data can be treated as anonymised (so not subject to the UK GDPR) depending on ‘whose hands’ it is in. For example, when the user does not have access to the encryption key and cannot re-identify persons even with available data, it may be deemed anonymous in their hands.
- 4.11 However, the ICO notes that the ‘whose hands’ approach does *not* apply when disclosing information to an organisation who is acting as a joint controller or as a processor. If information is personal data in the controller’s hands, it will also be personal data in the hands of any joint controllers or processors, regardless of their technical or contractual ability to identify the people it relates to.
- 4.12 This stance is likely to cause confusion in the research community, specifically in the context of a SDE, as it is contrary to existing practice. In some circumstances, the host of a SDE will be a processor, when it does not have any purpose of its own for hosting and processing the data, beyond providing a service to the data contributors, and when it does not determine any of the essential means of processing. Such SDEs will receive pseudonymous data, from which other quasi-identifiers have been removed. Accordingly, it is *not likely that they could identify the data subjects and – indeed – it would be an offence under the Data Protection Act 2018 for them to try to do so. Prior to the ICO guidance, such SDEs had considered that the data was anonymous in their hands; they will now need to rethink.* There is also a possibility that multiple organisations deciding to collaborate to set up a SDE would be seen as joint controllers, as they would be processing data because of a common decision between them. The consequence of the ICO’s guidance is that release of data to any of those organisations must be treated as release of personal data – irrespective of whether it is actually possible for the recipient to identify individuals. Given the prevailing understanding among those using SDEs, additional guidance from the ICO on anonymisation with specific focus on the status of data accessed for research in SDEs may be needed to clarify these issues.

Position under the law of confidence

- 4.13 Case law establishes that the law of confidence is concerned to protect a patient's privacy; provided this is protected when information is disclosed (e.g. by making it unlikely to be able to identify the individual), then there is no breach of confidence³⁴. However, the cases do not set out a clear threshold for what amounts to identifiable information under the law of confidence.³⁵
- 4.14 Section 251 of the NHS Act does contain a definition of "confidential patient information". As noted above, section 251 allows regulations to be promulgated which require disclosure of patient information. The defined term, "*confidential patient information*" is used in this context, to restrict when the Secretary of State can compel information to be disclosed and to provide that, in the case of confidential patient information, this can only be done when the objectives cannot otherwise be reasonably be achieved. The definition is not, therefore, necessarily identical to that that would be applied under common law. However, it is a useful point of reference.
- 4.15 Section 251(11) provides that patient is confidential when the identity of the individual is ascertainable either from that information or from that information and other information which is in the possession of, or is likely to come into the possession of, the person processing the information. The definition is similar to that under data protection legislation – encompassing information that directly or indirectly allows identification. However, the focus on what is in the possession of the person carrying out the processing is narrower than recital 26 of UK GDPR (which looks at identifiability by the controller or any other person).
- 4.16 In practice, there seems to be considerable lack of clarity as to when patient information will be considered to be sufficiently non-identifiable as to mean that it can be disclosed without being in breach of confidence:
- 4.16.1 NHS Scotland Code of Practice for Health (para 9.1) states that pseudonymous information would still be subject to the law of confidence³⁶;
- 4.16.2 The ICO, HRA, NHSE and others have published an agreed anonymisation standard³⁷ which states that "*Data can be rendered anonymous in this context even if it retains a pseudonym.*"

³⁴ R v Department of Health, ex parte Source Informatics [2001] QB 424

³⁵ In the Source Informatics case, the court was not asked to determine whether Source's scheme was actually effective; this was presumed and the Court of Appeal noted that there was a striking lack of any case law on the topic

³⁶ Protecting Patients Confidentiality

³⁷ <https://www.hra.nhs.uk/planning-and-improving-research/research-planning/how-were-supporting-data-driven-technology/overview-legal-requirements-using-health-and-care-data-development-and-deployment-data-driven-technologies/>

- 4.17 However, the Northern Irish Code of Practice on Protecting the Confidentiality of Service User Information notes that pseudonymous information is not anonymous, but suggests that where full anonymisation cannot be achieved that the disclosing party must consider risks to confidentiality, so as to ensure that there is not inappropriate disclosure – seemingly anticipating that disclosures could still be possible provided there is no risk to individuals³⁸.
- 4.18 As a result, the health and social care sectors often look to ICO guidance on anonymisation and identifiability. However, this guidance is – of course focused – on data protection definitions and is not determinative of the position under the law of confidence. As briefly suggested by the examples above, there is a particular divergence of views as to whether pseudonymous data is subject to the law of confidence or whether it must be fully anonymised before it ceases to be confidential. A policy decision needs to be made on this point and guidance published so that organisations can be confident which duties apply to the information.

Practical experience

- 4.19 For research projects and studies there is not always an immediately obvious answer as to whether the data to be processed will be personal/identifiable, as the assessment depends on a number of factors, including the data fields being processed, the technical measures in place and the roles of the parties. In HDR UK's experience there is no consensus yet on whether individual-level data that is in an SDE with direct identifiers removed is personal data/ identifiable or not. Different SDEs take different approaches to this, resulting in different governance models for similar data sets. This variance and uncertainty affects many studies and adds time and cost to getting access to health data for research purposes.
- 4.20 Currently there is an absence of clear guidance and caselaw³⁹ on this topic in the UK, especially in respect of scientific research using longitudinal data. Clear guidance from the ICO as the UK's data protection regulator could largely resolve this issue – at least so far as data protection legislation is concerned. Further targeted sectoral guidance or statements would also be needed to address the status of confidential patient information especially where pseudonymisation techniques have been applied.
- 4.21 The anticipated ICO guidance on anonymisation and Trusted Research Environments (TREs, also known as SDEs) could provide the clarity needed for parties to be able to reach a consensus on this. Where there are divergent views, the parties would be able to point to this guidance and work through how it would apply to the specifics of their study/project to reach an agreed approach (and one that is correct in the eyes of the ICO).

³⁸ See [Revised Code of Practice on Protecting the Confidentiality of Service User Information V2 – April 2019 \(Northern Ireland\)](#)

³⁹ Given the historic lack of caselaw and that by its very nature there is no guarantee of a case being brought on the specific points where guidance is lacking, caselaw cannot be relied upon to resolve these issues

- 4.22 The law of confidence is a separate body of law, and in the context of health research the question of whether patient information has been sufficiently de-identified as to cease to be confidential is in an even more important one than whether it has ceased to be personal data under data protection laws. While the status of data as personal or not would affect the obligations of the various parties, it would not – as a matter of principle – stop processing for research. Data protection law privileges the processing of personal data for medical purposes, public health purposes and purposes of scientific research – and allows this to take place without patient consent. However, under the law of confidence, secondary use of confidential patient information for research purposes is more difficult (in some cases impossible) without patient consent.
- 4.23 As some aspects of data protection legislation address similar concerns to those addressed by the law of confidence, and as the concepts and terminology are similar, guidance issued by ICO will inevitably be of interest to, if not determinative of, the question under the law of confidence. However, adopting the same approach to the definition of when patient data is identifiable may have the effect of making valuable research more difficult. Accordingly, having clear guidance on this point is linked to resolving wider questions of facilitating further use of confidential patient information.

5 Fragmented governance, lack of consistent processes and standards

- 5.1 Even where a path has been identified for compliance with both data protection laws and the common law duty of confidentiality, there remain challenges with access to data for research. Whilst common law and data protection laws are frequently cited as the reasons for delaying and preventing data access, in HDR UK's experience data access processes pose an even greater challenge. Data custodians across the UK have implemented individual processes for assessing and approving data access requests which can be challenging and time-consuming to navigate. This is a particular challenge for researchers seeking to link data from multiple custodians, whereby each data controller often requires the same information in different formats, with multiple review and approval steps.⁴⁰ Streamlining and standardising these processes across the many organisations holding health and health-relevant data would solve many of the current challenges for the research community.
- 5.2 Currently there is also a lack of model forms of agreement to permit health data sharing which results in parties needing to individually negotiate data access terms. As noted in the *Sudlow Review*⁴¹ this takes time to agree and places a burden on staff who are negotiating the terms of access, which in turn discourages them from engaging in data sharing for research purposes. This situation is in contrast to clinical trials where HRA model agreements are more widely used. HDR UK is working with the HRA and others including NHSE to create model agreements specifically for data access within TREs/SDEs.
- 5.3 Aligned data access governance models must be underpinned by robust and trusted data governance frameworks. The ONS developed the “Five Safes” framework to support organisational decision-making regarding how to balance protection of confidentiality whilst enabling data use for research. The Pan-UK Data Governance Steering Group (a group of the UK Health Data Research Alliance convened by HDR UK in partnership with ONS, ADR UK and others) is leading development of the “safeGUARDS” – a broader set of governance principles and aligned commitments which incorporate Five Safes and wider social and professional considerations. The safeGUARDS are designed to support a broad set of considerations and balance confidentiality, with research utility and the factors known to influence the ‘social licence’ for using individuals’ data in research.

⁴⁰ <https://bmjopen.bmj.com/content/11/8/e047575>

⁴¹ See Sudlow Review – page 39

6 Conclusion

- 6.1 There are currently a number of issues which organisations involved in research must overcome to be able to access the data they need. These issues exist both under the common law duty of confidentiality and data protection laws, as set out above. Together these issues delay research and, in some cases, even prevent it from taking place, either because the law does not provide a mechanism for research to take place at all, or – where it does – due to the costs incurred to navigate these barriers or the fear of a legal misstep. Data access governance models are fragmented across a complex ecosystem of data custodians and challenging to navigate. Action is needed to remove these barriers so that data access in the UK for health research can be more streamlined and cost-effective. This paper sets out a number of recommendations above to resolve these issues, namely:

Addressing the common law duty:

- 6.1.1 Broader use of the COPI Regulations to permit processing of data relating to “other risks to public health” and wider issuance of COPI notices to address research questions outside of Covid and mandate the sharing of data, provided that appropriate safeguards are in place including to ensure research is in the public benefit
- 6.1.2 Policy decisions and clearer regulatory guidance to assist organisations with navigating these complex legal rules to ensure a consistent approach and improve confidence in sharing data for medical research;
- 6.1.3 Potentially broadening the scope of the DEA to include health data in the voluntary disclosure provisions, although this risks creating overlap with regime for health data set out in the NHS Act and COPI Regulations and adding complexity and requires careful consideration; and
- 6.1.4 Amending the Statistic’s Board’s accreditation criteria to address health research.

Addressing data protection challenges

- 6.1.5 Drafting bespoke international data transfer terms for research purposes with accompanying guidance – this could either be done by ICO and/or by the Secretary of State (terms adopted by the Secretary of State could also remove the need for transfer risk assessments).

Addressing lack of clarity around anonymisation of data for research

- 6.1.6 Additional guidance from the ICO on anonymisation with specific focus on the status of individual-level data accessed for research in SDEs.

Addressing divergent governance models

- 6.1.7 Creating regulator-approved governance models, templates and toolkits which can be used with confidence.

- 6.2 Many of these changes are under consideration or already in progress and we would welcome commitment from the UK government and ICO to process them to conclusion, in consultation with the research community and the HRA, National Data Guardian (NDG), ONS, HDR UK and any other bodies identified as being relevant to the changes suggested above.

- 6.3 Finally, but most importantly, people living in the UK rightly expect transparency and accountability from organisations using their data for research. Loss of public trust presents a greater barrier to wider data linkage and access than the current legal regime, and public trust must be strengthened. Any legal reform in this area should be implemented with full and meaningful public transparency, involvement and engagement.

Annex 1: The current legal landscape

Law/ Regulation	Territorial Scope	Mandatory or Voluntary Disclosure	Approvals Process	Amendment Process
Confidentiality				
COPI Regulations	England & Wales	Regulation 3 – mandatory Regulations 5 & 6 – voluntary	Case by case & class basis (e.g. CAG precedent set pathways)	Can be amended by secondary legislation
NHS Act 2007	England	Mandatory & Voluntary (see COPI regulations)	See COPI regulations	Primary legislation needed to amend
Digital Economy Act	UK-wide	Voluntary	Case by case	Primary legislation needed to amend
Statistics and Registration Service Act 2007	UK-wide	Mandatory	Case by case	Can be amended by secondary legislation
Public Interest	UK-wide	Voluntary	Case by case.	N/A
Data Protection				
UK GDPR and DPA 2018	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Privileges medical research purposes + Uncertainty around whether considered anonymised vs personal data and around the roles of parties + Restrictions on international data transfers (these restrictions cannot fully be resolved under the current regime) 			

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